

Bio 21 – Homeopathic Medication for Teething: Dental Perspective Redefined

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ABSTRACT: Dentistry is a unique branch of medicine in which various oral problems are treated. The use of traditional medicine is common in dental practice and is widely used to treat dental problems since olden days. Homeopathy as an element of holistic dentistry provides effective treatment to the patients while reducing side effects. Bio 21, a homeopathic medication hence has been widely used for treatment of teething problems thus reducing common symptoms that are manifested. This literature based article is highlighting the possible role of Bio 21 in management of teething problems.

KEYWORDS: Homeopathy, Dentistry, Bio21, Teething, Complementary and Alternative Medicine

I. INTRODUCTION

Homeopathy is one of the allied branches of medical sciences which has shown several miracles in the management & treatment of rare cases. It was originated from the Greek terminology ‘Homoios’ which means similar & ‘Pathos’ which means suffering or sickness.

The use of homeopathy in dentistry is a contemplative innovation that opens up various new clinical opportunities, particularly since many symptoms of systemic disease are first observed in oral cavity, like in case of teething in children, in which dental process causes various systemic manifestations like diarrhea, fever and many more.

We believe that as more dentists discover the effectiveness of using complementary treatments, homeopathy will make significant contributions both to dental health as well as overall well-being of patients.

A general concern among the parents is how to cope with their toddlers during the teething phase. Homeopathy is based on the basic beliefs ‘Like cures Likes’ wherein disease can be cured by a substance that produces similar symptoms in healthy people and ‘Law of Minimum dose’ wherein the notion says that lower the dose of medication, greater its effectiveness.

Prescribing homeopathic medication such as Bio-21 can be a boon for pediatric dentists. Consumption of Bio-21 can be a probable cure for teething problems. Pediatric patients of the age group 6months to 3 years undergo natural process of teething wherein eruption of primary dentition or in layman terms ‘milk teeth’ takes place.

During this phase, parents often find it hard to handle the children as the latter face various symptoms. These can be fever, loss of appetite, general irritability, bleeding and swelling of gums, diarrhea, constipation, gnawing, rashes, vomiting, sleep disturbances and many more which may last from one day to thirty days, approximately, depending on the individual. In order to alleviate these symptoms, parents give medication according to symptoms seen such as paracetamol for fever.

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Recently, while interacting with parents of pediatric patients at MRDC, Faridabad, Bio-21 as a probable solution for teething problems was found.

It is available in tablet form as a combination of Calcarea phosphorica and Ferrum phosphoricum in equal proportion. Calcarea phosphorica, especially, may be helpful to a child whose teeth erupt late, with pain in the gums and sleeping troubles. Sometimes also indicated in cases of irritability, disrupted eating patterns and gum issues.

Bio 21 is quite effective in providing relief from bleeding and swollen gums. It alleviates fever and increases appetite in children. It is quite successful in managing decaying teeth and reducing bad taste in mouth. Bio 21 is available under various brand names in the market therefore dosage may vary accordingly. There should be at least 30-60 minutes' gap between medicine and food consumption. It should ideally not be given along with allopathic medication. No known side effects have been put forward yet.

Though homeopathy is an emerging field and a lot of research is ongoing but the interaction among various drugs is still unknown. Generally, allergic reactions i.e. rashes are commonly manifested.

Some other widely used homeopathic medicines for teething are Chamomilla 30C and Belladonna 30 C. Chamomilla is most widely recognized for problems of erupting teeth. Belladonna is used when child has red, swollen gums and sleeping disturbances. But these may have shown some side effects.

Interaction with the parents have resulted in quite a satisfactory response in regard to Bio-21. It is as of now a potent, nontoxic drug for pediatric patients in order to deal with teething problems making it a quite useful solution for parents as well as pediatric dentists.

II. CONCLUSIONS

Whatever the combination of symptoms the individual faces during this phase, they all are all manifestation of single process i.e. teething which are unique to that individual. Homeopathy is not a replacement for oral hygiene habits and no particular evidence is present to support it, hence a note of caution should be applied. Dental treatments can never be completely natural, hence by utilizing the homeopathy medicine, some side effects can be avoided making it more bearable for the patients.

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